

A SURVEY ON ASSESSMENT OF ACTIVE BASED LEARNING IN TEACHING AT PRIMARY

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Abstract:

Activity based learning has been meticulously designed according to the needs, demands, likes and fancies of learners at primary level. When the merits of the ABL method and learning outcomes of students were realized ideal and suitable, it is now practiced in all the government schools in Tamil Nadu from the year of 2007 onwards. SSA has implemented the "Activity Based learning" methodology as a quality improvement programme to enhance learning level of all children at primary level. The methodology is based on the Yashpal committee report -Learning without Burden. Activity Based learning method has revolutionized the whole educational process in Tamil Nadu. This method has simplified the process of teaching as well as learning. This method is more logical and natural; and a lot of exposure has been given to children to learn in their own natural environment. Slow learners gain confidence in this method and learn on their own pace. Here the pupil completes the syllabus and not the teachers. Grouping is formed according to the pupils' achievement. Quite a large number of self learning activities are given for the children to learn by themselves. Children has self -satisfaction, a sense of achievement and feeling of happiness in completing each card. There is also provision for the fast learners to go fast at their own speed and pace.

Key Words: Active Based Learning and Primary Level

Need for the Study:

ABL has brought about a revolution and has rewritten the history of education at primary level in Tamil Nadu. The strategy of teaching-learning in ABL induces student centred approach. It spotted the chunks of learning in the armor of education system and make it more effective, productive, contemporary progressive way of our education. It nurtures a unique concept in teaching that explores the innate talents in the pupils and makes them academically strong, physically and mentally fit to lead a successful life. When the pupils complete their primary education, they are brimming with knowledge, experience and confidence to meet challenges in their education. The learning difficulties have been spotted and cause for the same is diagnosed for remedial teaching in primary level of learning. Through the design of ABL is based on many theoretical aspects in order to make the teaching-learning process more enjoyable and beneficial to the budding learners. The practicability of ABL and its net application and the effectiveness is not analysed till date. The pivotal need of this investigation is to detail the beneficial aspects and the difficulties in practice.

Objectives of the Study:

The specific objectives of the study are listed below.

- To assess the ABL Teaching-Learning at IV standard level.
- To find out whether there is a significant difference in the Assessment of ABL Teaching-Learning among IV standard pupils in terms of select independent variables viz., Gender, Family Type, and Number of Brothers and Sisters.

Terms and Definitions:

Assessment of ABL Teaching – refers to the opinion of IV standard pupils in respect of teacher activities and pupils performance inside the class rooms.

Primary Level - refers to those who are studying in IV standard under Tamil Nadu State Board Syllabus in Madurai district.

Survey - refers to one of the techniques to collect the data in Educational research.

Variables of the Study:

Dependent Variable:

Assessment of ABL Teaching-Learning

Independent Variables:

- Gender : Male / Female
- Family Type : Joint / Nuclear
- Number of Brothers and Sisters : Below 3 / 3 and above

Hypotheses of the Study:

The following hypotheses have been formulated for verification in this study.

- Assessment of ABL Teaching-Learning is satisfactory among IV standard pupils.

- Gender exerts a significant influence on the assessment of ABL Teaching-Learning among IV standard pupils.
- Family Type exerts a significant influence on the assessment of ABL Teaching-Learning among IV standard pupils.
- Number of Brothers and Sisters exerts a significant influence on the assessment of ABL Teaching-Learning among IV standard pupils.

Methodology – In – Brief:

- Design : Descriptive
- Method : Normative study
- Technique : Survey

Sample:

A random sample of 350 IV standard pupils from Primary and Middle Schools in Madurai Revenue District with due representation to the select variables viz., Gender, Family Type and Number of Brothers and Sisters.

Tools Used:

The tools used for data collection are as follows:

- General Information sheet structured by the Investigator.
- Assessment of ABL Teaching-Check List was developed by Kanniammal, K.(2011).

Statistical Treatments:

- ‘t’- test for significance of difference between the means of large independent samples.

Related Studies:

Suydan, Marilyn and Higgins (1977), Reached on the conclusion that ABL in elementary mathematics is more effective than traditional method of teaching. According to Brophy (1995) students learn concepts in depth if these concepts are learnt in a different context which may include classroom lecture, laboratory experiments, textbook readings etc. Moreover, they can apply this knowledge in novel situations in a better way. To familiarize students with scientific knowledge is one of the aims of science teaching (Carey & Smith, 1993) so they can apply this knowledge in problem solving situations. Science is more than collecting and manipulating data or memorizing knowledge. According to National Research Council (1996), it is “a process of inquiry that requires asking questions, observing, data exploration and data manipulation. It requires learning to apply and generalize scientific knowledge”. Creating such learning environment requires engaging learners in different activities.

Hake (1998), Found that ABL significantly improves conceptual understanding of the students in a physics class. Magno et al. (2005) reached on the conclusion that “the classes receiving the PBL activity on memory had significantly higher performance accuracy in the test and had higher attitude as compared with the other classes who received instruction through traditional method”. While conducting research on teaching experimental economics for high schools, Brock and Lopus (2004) concluded that “*ABL do a good job of satisfying the conditions sufficient for economic experiments*”.

Owen Conlan, Ian O’Keeffe, Aoife Brady and Vincent Wade(2011), “Principles for Designing Activity-based Personalized eLearning”. This study has described the principles behind the combination of personalized content and services may be used to create activity-based personalized distance learning offerings. Through combining the methodologies seen in the domains of service composition and personalized learning a service-oriented approach to personalized learning activities may be realized. The principles espoused by the multi-model, metadata driven approach have been shown as appropriate guidelines for achieving successful personalizations that engage learners in activity-based distance learning opportunities. The work described in this paper is currently being applied in the European Commission FP6 IST project iClass to provide rich personalised learning experiences to K12 school children.

Analysis and Interpretation of Data:

Assessment of ABL Teaching-Learning among IV Standard Pupils:

The average score of the assessment of ABL teaching-learning of IV standard pupils is found to be 36, while the theoretical average is 19 only. Hence the assessment of ABL teaching-learning among IV standard pupils is found to be above the average level. It means that the assessment of ABL teaching-learning among IV standard pupils is found to be highly satisfactory.

Assessment of ABL Teaching-Learning and Gender:

The statistical measures and the results of test of significance of difference between the mean scores of Assessment of ABL Teaching-Learning among IV standard pupils in terms of Gender is presented in Table 1.

Variable	Sub Variables	N	Mean	Sd	‘T’ Value	Significance at 0.05 Level
Gender	Male	216	35.59	3.47	-3.248	Significant
	Female	134	36.65	2.61		

The calculated 't' value (-3.248) is greater than the table value (1.96) at 0.05 level of significance. This shows that there is a significant difference between male and female pupils in the possession of assessment of ABL teaching-learning. It can be inferred from the above finding that the female pupils' Assessment of ABL Teaching-Learning is more than their counterparts studying in IV standard.

Assessment of ABL Teaching-Learning and Family Type:

The statistical measures and the results of test of significance of difference between the mean scores of Assessment of ABL Teaching-Learning among IV standard pupils in terms of family type is presented in Table 2.

Variable	Sub Variables	N	Mean	Sd	'T' Value	Significance at 0.05 Level
Family Type	Nuclear	302	36.14	3.09	1.796	Not Significant
	Joint	48	35.10	3.78		

The calculated 't' value (1.796) is lesser than the table value (1.96) at 0.05 level of significance. This shows that there is no significant difference between Nuclear and Joint family pupils in the possession of assessment of ABL teaching-learning. From the above finding it can be inferred that, Family type does not play a vital role in the Assessment of ABL Teaching-Learning among IV standard pupils.

Assessment of ABL Teaching-Learning and Number of Brothers and Sisters:

The statistical measures and the results of test of significance of difference between the mean scores of Assessment of ABL Teaching-Learning among IV standard pupils in terms of No. of Brothers and Sisters is presented in Table 3.

Teaching - Learning: Number of Brothers and Sisters - Wise

Variable	Sub Variables	N	Mean	SD	'T' Value	Significance at 0.05 Level
Number of brothers and sisters	Below Three	256	36.59	3.36	6.514	Significant
	Three and above	94	34.18	2.98		

The calculated 't' value (6.514) is greater than the table value (1.96) at 0.05 level of significance. This shows that there is a significant difference in the number of brothers and sisters between Below Three and Three and above pupils in the possession of assessment of ABL teaching-learning. It can be inferred from the above finding that, the Number of brothers and sisters below three pupils' Assessment of ABL Teaching-Learning is more than the number of brothers and sisters three and above pupils studying in IV standard.

Educational Implications:

The following measures may be attempted for the enrichment of ABL Teaching-Learning:

- Pupils participation should be enhanced further.
- Adequate teachers should be appointed in order to facilitate the ABL programme implemented effectively.
- Wastage in usage of the ABL Teaching-Learning materials should be minimized.
- Community participation in the primary school level should be encouraged.
- Parents should be made aware of the ABL Teaching-Learning process and their participation is an essential aspect for the success of the programme.
- Simultaneously, other activities like sports and games, extra-curricular activities etc. should be encouraged among pupils of IV standard level.
- It is a right time to review this ABL Teaching-Learning in schools as it has been under practice for five years.
- This type of studies will be surely a worth mentioning in the overall assessment of ABL Teaching-Learning at primary level.

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